

Emotional Intelligence and Transformational Leadership: A Correlational Study in Telecom Sector of Pakistan

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Abstract

This study investigates a linkage amongst “Transformational leadership (TFL)” and “Emotional Intelligence (EI)” by using a trait model. These two, from the perspective of literature, support each other. Empirical research to validate the results in Pakistani settings were done. The data was gathered from the managers² of the telecom segment via two standardized instruments “TEIQue-SF” and “MLQ-5X” and distributed via google forms. The study is cross-sectional and quantitative with sample size 440. A stratified sampling method was employed and later the analysis was done using SPSS. Respondents’ socio demographical profile was generated. The reliability of the instruments used was found to be acceptable. Correlation and regression analyses of the data revealed a moderate to the high positive correlation between EI and TFL along with its dimensions. Moreover, the relationship was found to be statistically significant.

Keywords: Transformational leadership, Emotional Intelligence, Telecom Sector, Pakistan

Introduction

Pakistan has 164 million cellular subscribers with a teledensity of 77.69 % including 76 million broadband subscribers. In the financial year 2018-19, there was an inflow of 288 million dollars as direct foreign investment in the telecom sector. The revenues generated in this sector have been gradually rising in the last decade with a contribution of 146 billion to the national exchequer in the financial year 2018-19. The Telecom sector provides many opportunities to undeveloped nations [1],[2]. Despite this true potential of this sector which requires comparatively low investment has not been explored. The challenges faced by the management in the 21st century have placed special requirements on the leadership programs where the relationship that emerges between leaders and their followers is very emotional.

Emotional Intelligence (EI)

“75% of careers are derailed for reasons related to emotional competencies, including inability to handle interpersonal problems; unsatisfactory team leadership during times of difficulty or conflict; or inability to adapt to change or elicit trust.”

The Centre for Creative Leadership

The concept of EI has become immensely significant in the present times and is defined as “The ability to monitor one’s own and other’s emotions, to discriminate among them, and to use the information to guide one’s thinking and actions” [3]. This attribute offers a range of expertise, such as being able to maintain interactions, impact, and motivate others. It is an essential element for sustainable performance in the contemporary workforce, affecting results, giving high team commitment, financial freedom, rapid development, high productivity, and collective engagement. The theory of EI shows that real knowledge is

not just a matter of logical thought and an understanding of complex concepts. Emotional Quotient is a measure of EI and enables an individual in handling almost anything with a degree of balance and maturity. All across literature, researchers in the field of social behavioral science exchanged numerous meanings, explanations, and the significance of emotions. There exist, three main models of EI, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Models of Emotional Intelligence

Transformational Leadership (TFL)

“Transformational leaders don’t start by denying the world around them. Instead, they describe a future they’d like to create instead.”

– Seth Godin[4]

Leadership defined by Burns [5] is as: “Leaders inducing followers to act for certain goals that represent the values and the motivations—the wants and needs, the aspirations and expectations—of both leaders and followers. Besides, the genius of leadership lies in the manner in which leaders see and act on their own and their followers’ values and motivations”. TFL requires the leader to identify with his followers. In exchange, they regard him as their role model and seek to achieve their common dream with him. An essential precondition for a transformational leader is to embolden his followers to exploit their potential to achieve their ultimate objective of becoming leaders themselves. The construct of Transformational Leadership comprises five dimensions [6] shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Dimensions of Transformational Leadership

Study Objectives

- To get an insight into the exhibition of TFL behavior and the presence of EI in managers of the telecom sector.
- To throw light and explore the association of EI with TFL and its dimensions.

Literature Review

“It is very important to understand that emotional intelligence is not the opposite of intelligence, it is not the triumph of heart overhead it is the unique intersection of both.”

- David Caruso

Exploration of an association between the concept of EI and TFL has become a topic of interest for many researchers. A lot of work has been done on exploring the relationship [7], [8]. Research studies have lately started questioning how some persons exhibit a more transformative leadership style and if emotional intelligence serves a leading role. Therefore, various research relating EI to TL found that people who find themselves transformational have recognized their own as well as the emotional feelings of people around them. They can communicate their feelings to everyone else, utilize EI to resolve issues, and manipulate sentiments effectively.

Siegling et al. [9] in a quantitative study in a European multinational company examined if trait emotional efficacy differentiated leaders from a non-leader. The study studied 96 employees using Existing intelligence test scores with tenure, age, gender, as control variables. In a logistic regression model, Trait Emotional intelligence, gender and, cognitive capabilities were/ significant predictors. Moreover, all the participants (leaders and non-leaders) scored higher than the results found in the TEIQue standardized study carried out by K.V. Petrides [10].

The association between EI and TFL in a trading firm in the UK has been explored by Duckett and Macfarlane [11]. The conclusion of the study was EI and TFL are strongly associated. The study highlighted the importance of TFL behavior in all spheres of the organization’s life cycle.

Hur et al. [12] studied the mediating role of transformation leadership between EI and team outcomes .data was collected in south Korean public organizations from 859 employees. The study was quantitative and showed a clear link from a theoretical perspective among EI and TFL.

Raina and Sharma [13] carried out a correlational study in 47 entrepreneurs of Rajasthan to establish a linkage between EI and leadership in India’s business sector. Effectiveness, EI, and TFL behavior confirmed the presence of a positive relation.

An exploratory study in the United Kingdom by Barling et al [14] consisting of 49 managers and 187 sub-subordinates has conducted three questionnaires with the results showing that EI is correlated with three dimensions of TFL. In comparison, there was no connection with EI between active and passive management through exception and laissez-faire management. The researcher concluded that further work would be warranted.

Ibrahim et al.[15] in a quantitative study in the services sector of Pakistan using MLQ, WLEIS, and OCQ investigated TFL and commitment in an organization with the moderating role of EI. The research concluded that transformative leaders with EI would draw from their workers a better normative commitment.

Mustafa and Sattar [16] investigated the connections among EI and the transformative leadership of educational leaders in Pakistan's higher education sector. The sample consisted of 345 faculty members of the top-performing universities of Pakistan. The findings showed that EI is the cornerstone of the behavior of a transformational leader. The findings proved that EI aspects are significantly associated with transformative leadership. This study concluded that emotionally smart leaders will display transformational leadership better.

Batool [17] used the “Emotional Intelligence Scale” [18] and “Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire-5X” [6] for examining the connection between EI and leadership styles based on FRLT in college teachers. A sample of 100 teachers was used. The results show that EI has a positive relationship with the transformative style of leadership.

Harms and Crede [19] in their study “Emotional Intelligence and Transformational Leadership: A Meta-Analysis” provides analytic proof of the association between EI and TFL by basing their results on 62 independent samples. EI was positively associated with TFL and contingent reward behaviors but was not or adversely related to management-by-exception or laissez-faire leadership behaviors.

Research Framework

Figure 3. Research Model

Hypothesis

- H1: Emotional Intelligence is associated with Transformational Leadership.
- H2: Emotional Intelligence is associated with Idealised Influence (Attributed).
- H3: Emotional Intelligence is associated with Idealised Influence (Behaviour).
- H4: Emotional Intelligence is associated with Inspirational Motivation.
- H5: Emotional Intelligence is associated with Intellectual Stimulation.
- H6: Emotional Intelligence is associated with Individualized Consideration.

Methodology

The examination of the relationship was a descriptive study and for fulfilling the objectives, data was primarily obtained through primary sources. The data gathered was from the 440 respondents from the telecom sector of Pakistan through a stratified sampling procedure. The information so collected was analyzed quantitatively. In this cross-sectional study, data collected through a survey for the two constructs, EI and TFL. For the EI construct, the model administered was the Trait model and the questionnaire was “Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire - Short Form (TEIQue-SF)” and “Multifactor leadership

questionnaire (MLQ-5X)” for TFL construct. The survey had a demographic portion which gave us the socio-demographical profile of the respondents.

Data Analysis

The respondents' gender ratio for males and females was 73% and 26%. Maximum response was received from respondents of age group 21-30 yrs followed by 31-40 yrs and 41-50 yrs. The ratio of married respondents was more 52.5 %. The mean score of both EI and TFL were above the average of 5.05 (SD=0.63) and 3.32 (SD=0.61). The Socio-demographic profile of the respondents of this research is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Demographic and Mean Statistics

Measure	Classification	Frequency	Percentage %
Gender	Female	119	27
	Male	321	73
Age	21 - 30 yrs	191	43.4
	31 - 40 yrs	185	42
	41 - 50 yrs	64	14.6
Marital status	Married	231	52.5
	Single	209	47.5
TFL (Mean)		3.32 (SD = 0.61)	
EI (Mean)		5.05 (SD = 0.63)	

The reliability of the instruments was checked by measuring the value of Cronbach alpha. Both the instruments were highly reliable with the value of 0.876 and 0.843 for TFL and EI respectively as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Reliability

Construct	Total Questions	Reliability
TFL	20	0.876
EI	30	0.843

The correlation test was used to check the relationship and accept/reject the hypotheses. All null hypotheses were rejected as correlation coefficients of EI with TFL and its dimensions were positive and statistically significant ($P < 0.01$). The correlation coefficients are shown in Table 3. IA presented the highest correlation in dimensions of TFL with EI ($r = 0.757$).

Table 3. Correlations

	EI	IA	IB	IM	IS	IC	TFL
EI	1						
IA	.488**	1					
IB	.757**	.696**	1				
IM	.667**	.733**	.900**	1			
IS	.750**	.848**	.895**	.827**	1		
IC	.406**	.682**	.659**	.639**	.750**	1	
TFL	.792**	.887**	.921**	.912**	.959**	.821**	1

**."Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)".

Regression Analysis

Table 4. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.792 ^a	.784	.784	.05419

a. Predictors: (Constant), EI

EI and TFL are highly correlated. **78.4 %** of the variability in TFL can be attributed to EI which was quite high.

Table 5. ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	77.307	1	77.307	14046.210	.000 ^b
Residual	1.227	369	.006		
Total	78.534	370			

a. Dependent Variable: TFL

b. Predictors: (Constant), EI

The regression model predicted the outcome variable significantly ($p < 0.0005$).

Table 6. Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
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	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.089	.037		2.442	.015
1 EI	.797	.008	.792	118.517	.000

a. Dependent Variable: TFL

Regression equation generated is :

$$\text{Transformational Leadership} = 0.089 + 0.797 (\text{Emotional Intelligence})$$

Discussion

In this study, conceptual connections between EI and TFL have been investigated and empirically verified by evaluating the primary data collected through valid and reliable instruments. Compared to the general population, the managers of the telecom sector tested above the mean EI and TFL. The results showed the telecom leaders in this sample to have a high degree of EI characteristics [10] and TFL-style attributes. Our study results show that the EI / TFL correlation among telecom sector leaders is significantly high and positive. The widespread nature of our research supports the results of Harms and Crede [19] meta-analysis. Moreover, EI relationship with sub-dimensions of TFL was also found to be significant and range from moderate to high suggesting that an emotionally intelligent person is more likely to display transformative leadership behaviour and is seen as inspiring, inspiring, moral, and revolutionary as earlier reported by Hackett and Hortman [20]. These individuals will clearly define levels of success, track performance, and reward achieving objectives which all have a positive effect on performance [21].

“Emotional intelligence accounts for 80 percent of career success”

– Daniel Goleman[22]

Limitations

The instruments version employed in this study for EI and TFL were self-reporting only. In the future, multi-rating instruments can be used to assess the population to avoid response bias. Moreover, the Trait model of EI has been used, further research can be done on doing a comparative study using Ability and Mixed models of EI. The study settings were cross-sectional. More work is warranted on developing EI in respondents at the initial stage and measuring its effect on TFL at a later stage.

Conclusion

Transformational leadership is founded on faith and dedication displayed by the subordinates which are further transformed into extraordinary achievements and increased productivity. This work supports the argument on the value of EI in the management process. The productive association between EI and TFL allows organizations to integrate it into their management programs and recruitment of employees. Telecom companies should also take steps for educating workers on approaches to improve and promote their EI to raise emotional awareness. An leader who can control his / her conduct and also consider those of his / her associates is considered to be emotionally intelligent. Such leaders can motivate employees to work towards institutional strategic objectives by knowing their subordinates, thereby enhancing organizational effectiveness. EI serves as among the biggest indicators of TFL, as is apparent from the information collected from literary analysis. The convergence of mind and heart, the potential to recognize and incorporate emotions as a method of communication and impact for their followers, are qualities of an emotionally intelligent leader.

“EQ is . . . the strongest driver of leadership and personal excellence”

- Travis Bradberry

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